

Reduced Reservoir Quality in the Triassic Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone of the Southern Netherlands: Insights from a new Offshore Well

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The Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone (LVS) in the southern Netherlands, part of the Main Buntsandstein Subgroup, has been a reservoir targeted for hydrocarbon exploration for decades. However, recently it has also been considered for potential deep geothermal energy and/or underground gas storage. The enigmatic distribution in reservoir quality requires site-specific evaluation. In order to get an understanding of the controlling processes, and ultimately to predict point of reservoir quality, the newly acquired offshore core section (Well-X) with reduced reservoir quality was evaluated in light of published data from nearby LVS wells.

This study reveals a strong control of primary depositional features (grain size and sorting) with a complex interplay of secondary diagenetic processes (e.g. recrystallisation, cementation, and dissolution). Despite early diagenetic carbonate cementation, which helped preserve initial porosity by stabilising the primary rock framework during compaction, cementation significantly occluded porosity and reduced reservoir quality. The reduced reservoir quality of Well-X is caused by a combination of local and regional controls, whereby reduced reservoir properties of finer-grained sediments are related to their (local) relative position within the braided river depositional setting. Diagenetic occlusion of porosity and associated reservoir quality reduction was mainly controlled at a regional scale by the palaeo-evolution of the Triassic coastline associated with the deposition of Middle to Late Triassic sabkha deposits and related reflux dolomitisation. These new insights from Well-X are crucial in predicting reservoir properties in the Buntsandstein reservoirs of relevance for future sustainable subsurface applications, such as geothermal exploration, as well as CO₂/H₂ storage.

Le grès de Lower Volpriehausen (LVS) dans le sud des Pays-Bas, qui fait partie du sous-groupe Main Buntsandstein, est depuis des décennies un réservoir ciblé pour l'exploration d'hydrocarbures. Cependant, il est récemment également envisagé pour son potentiel en matière d'énergie géothermique profonde et/ou de stockage souterrain de gaz. La distribution énigmatique de la qualité du réservoir nécessite une évaluation spécifique au site. Afin de comprendre les processus qui régissent la qualité du réservoir et, à terme, de prédire la qualité du réservoir, la nouvelle section de carottage offshore (puits X) présentant une qualité de réservoir réduite a été évaluée à la lumière des données publiées provenant de puits LVS voisins. Cette étude révèle une forte influence des caractéristiques sédimentaires primaires (granulométrie et tri) avec une interaction complexe de processus diagenétiques secondaires (par exemple, recristallisation, cimentation et dissolution). Malgré une cimentation diagenétique précoce des carbonates, qui a contribué à préserver la porosité initiale en stabilisant la structure rocheuse primaire pendant le compactage, la cimentation a considérablement réduit la porosité et la qualité du réservoir. La qualité réduite du réservoir du puits X est due à une combinaison de contrôles locaux et régionaux, les propriétés réduites des sédiments à grains plus fins étant liées à leur position relative (locale) dans le cadre sédimentaire du fleuve tressé. L'occlusion diagenétique de la porosité et la réduction associée de la qualité du réservoir ont été principalement contrôlées à l'échelle régionale par la paléo-évolution du littoral triasique associée au dépôt de sédiments sabkha du Trias moyen à supérieur et à la dolomitisation par reflux qui y est liée. Ces nouvelles connaissances issues du puits Well-X sont essentielles pour prédire les propriétés des réservoirs du Buntsandstein, qui sont pertinentes pour les futures applications souterraines durables, telles que l'exploration géothermique et le stockage de CO₂/H₂.

La arenisca Lower Volpriehausen (LVS) en el sur de los Países Bajos, que forma parte del subgrupo Main Buntsandstein, ha sido un yacimiento objetivo para la exploración de hidrocarburos durante décadas. Sin embargo, recientemente también se ha considerado su potencial para la energía geotérmica profunda y/o el almacenamiento subterráneo de gas. La enigmática distribución de la calidad del yacimiento requiere una evaluación específica del sitio. Con el fin de comprender los procesos que la controlan y, en última instancia, predecir la calidad del yacimiento, se evaluó la sección del núcleo marino recién adquirida (pozo X), con una calidad reducida, a la luz de los datos publicados de pozos LVS cercanos. Este estudio revela un fuerte control de las características de deposición primaria (tamaño y clasificación de los granos) con una compleja interacción de procesos diagenéticos secundarios (por ejemplo, recristalización, cementación y disolución). A pesar de la cementación diagenética temprana del carbonato, que ayudó a preservar la porosidad inicial al estabilizar la estructura primaria de la roca durante la compactación, la cementación ocluyó significativamente la porosidad y redujo la calidad del yacimiento. La reducción de la calidad del yacimiento del Pozo X se debe a una combinación de controles locales y regionales, por lo que la reducción de las propiedades del yacimiento de los sedimentos de grano más fino está relacionada con su posición relativa (local) dentro del entorno de deposición del río tressado. La oclusión diagenética de la porosidad y la consiguiente reducción de la calidad del yacimiento se vieron controladas principalmente a escala regional por la paleo-evolución de la costa triásica asociada al depósito de sedimentos sabkha del Triásico Medio al Triásico Tardío y la dolomitización por reflujo relacionada. Estos nuevos conocimientos obtenidos del pozo Well-X son cruciales para predecir las propiedades de los yacimientos de Buntsandstein, relevantes para futuras aplicaciones subterráneas sostenibles, como la exploración geotérmica y el almacenamiento de CO₂/H₂.

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1. Introduction

The Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone (LVS) in the southern Netherlands is one of the important clastic, lithified hydrocarbon reservoirs in the North Sea, a potential gas storage reservoir, and

is considered as a candidate for deep geothermal energy production [1–8]. The area of interest in this study is part of the Southern Permian Basin, which is known for its complex geological history, including episodes of continental deposition, marine transgressions, and significant tectonic

activity [5,9,10,11]. In continental sandstones, identifying potential reservoirs is quite challenging due to their vertical and horizontal heterogeneity. Equally important is understanding reservoir heterogeneities and the causes of reduced reservoir quality. Previous studies have highlighted diagenetic features that can explain some of the reduced reservoir quality in the North Sea Basin [10]. However, extrapolation between different well locations within the basin is not always possible and several uncertainties remain.

This emphasises the importance of an integrated analysis of the newly cored 49.09 m section of LVS in Well-X (development well). The latter was drilled in the Q-offshore block in the Broad Fourteens Basin (BFB). Lower-quality reservoir rocks were encountered which hampered hydrocarbon production. In this study we evaluate the petrographic and petrophysical data of Well-X, in light of published well data from neighbouring wells, L-blocks wells L02-02, L02-05, L02-06, L09-06 located north of Well-X, Gaag-02 (GAG-02), Haastreht-02 (HST-02), Keldonk-01 (KDK-01), Noordwijk-02 (NWK-02), Valkenburg-01 (VAL-01) and Werkendam-03 (WED-03), located in the West Netherlands Basin and KB-64, KB-98, KB-169, KB-172, KB-201 wells from the northeast of the Campine Basin [10,12,13,14,15,16], to understand the controls on LVS reservoir quality in the southern Netherlands, both at local and regional scales. Understanding these reservoir heterogeneities is vital for making at least partially predictive assessments regarding reservoir quality, in order to estimate risks and optimise reservoir development strategies for subsurface applications, such as hydrocarbon and geothermal exploration, as well as CO₂/H₂ storage.

2. Geological Settings

The studied Well-X is located in the offshore area of the Broad Fourteens Basin (BFB). The NW-SE striking BFB merges into the West Netherlands Basin (WNB) in the south and the Central Netherlands Basin (CNB) in the northeast. To the north, the Noord-Holland Platform and Cleaver Bank Highs are located (Fig. 1A) [5,17]. During the Early Triassic, the BFB was situated between 20° and 30°N (Fig. 1B) [3,11]. Semi-arid to arid climatic conditions prevailed in the completely landlocked area [5,7,10,18,19].

The Early Triassic was characterised by active tectonics [3,5,11,20,21,22] and

Figure 1: A) Structural framework of southern part of the Netherlands showing the basins, highs, platforms, and position of the studied well (red star), modified from [5, 11]. B) Palaeogeographical and tectonic map of Late Permian (255 Ma) showing that the Netherlands was located between 20° and 30° North (Black circle; modified from Global plate reconstruction (courtesy Shell) [3].

Period	Stage	Age (Ma)	Formation	Member	
Triassic	Late	200	Sleen Fm		
		204			
		218			
	Middle	Carnian	228	Keuper Fm <i>lower + middle Keuper</i>	Upper Keuper Claystone Dolomitic Keuper Red Keuper Claystone
			237		Red Keuper Evaporite Middle Keuper Claystone Main Keuper Evaporite Lower Keuper Claystone
		Ladinian	Muschelkalk Fm	237	Upper Muschelkalk Middle Muschelkalk Lower Muschelkalk
				245	Upper Rot Claystone Upper Rot Evaporite Intermed. Rot Claystone Main Rot Evaporite
	Early	Anisian	Rot Fm	Solling Claystone Basal Solling Sandstone	
				Olenekian	Hardeggen Fm
		Induan	Detfurth Fm		Upper Volpriehausen Sandstone Volpriehausen Clay-Siltstone Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone
			Volpriehausen Fm	Rogenstein Main Claystone	
		251	Lower Buntsandstein Fm		

Figure 2: Stratigraphic column displaying the position of the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone (red colour) unconformably overlying the Rogenstein Member (Lower Buntsandstein) modified from [5,11]. Vertical brown lines represent the missing Buntsandstein successions in Well-X.

fluvial-aeolian sedimentation occurred under ongoing local thermal uplift and/or subsidence, resulting in variations in lithofacies and lithostratigraphic unit thicknesses. The Main Buntsandstein Subgroup consists of three formations: Volpriehausen, Detfurth and Hardegsen, which are further subdivided into tectono-stratigraphic units based on cyclic alternation of sandstones and clay-siltstone (Fig. 2) [5,11]. The layers of interest for this study are the Lower Volpriehausen sandstones. The LVS predominantly consists of fluvial deposits with minor intercalations of aeolian sediments, and its thickness varies throughout the basin and reaches up to 200 metres [1,5,7,9,20,21]. In the studied well, the Volpriehausen Formation (Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone Member [LVS] and Upper Volpriehausen Clay-Siltstone Member [UVCS]) has an unconformable contact with the overlying Solling Formation reflecting non-deposition and/or erosion of the Detfurth and Hardegsen Formation. The latter relates to the major extensional tectonic phase of late Olenekian age, known as Hardegsen Unconformity [5,7,11], affected the thickness and spatial distribution of the Main Buntsandstein Subgroup. This Hardegsen uplift, with subsequent erosion, removed a significant part of the early Triassic successions on a regional scale in the Southern Permian Basins [5,7,9,19,20,21]. These Olenekian deposits are overlain by the marginal marine evaporitic Rot Formation, consisting of the Main Rot Evaporite Member [11].

3. Materials and Methods

Sedimentological and diagenetic characterisation of the 49.09 m cored Well-X section was carried out by examining the lithology and main sedimentary features (Fig. 3). Twenty plug samples (2.54 cm in diameter) were drilled and analysed to evaluate their mineralogical, petrographical, petrophysical and isotopic characteristics. Thin sections (perpendicular to bedding plane) were prepared from all samples. Six representative samples were selected for complementary analysis, including X-ray diffraction (XRD), helium porosity, and nitrogen gas permeability measurements (Table 1).

For XRD analysis, the outer edges of each rock sample were trimmed and ground manually using a porcelain mortar and pestle to avoid destruction of the mineral crystals. Approximately 1.8 g of each sample was then ground in a McCrone Micronizing Mill with the

Figure 3: Sedimentary log of Well-X (prepared in CoreIDRAW).

addition of an internal standard, ZnO (0.2 g) and ethanol (4 ml) for 5 min to obtain a uniformly sized powder. Ethanol was used to prevent dissolution of water-soluble minerals and minimise strain damage during grinding. After drying and sieving, the powdered sample was loaded into a metal holder with random orientation and analysed using an X-ray diffractometer. Diffractograms were interpreted using Quanta and X-ray Viewer software. For clay fraction analysis, oriented clay mounts were prepared from the <2 µm fraction using standard

sedimentation techniques. X-ray diffraction (XRD) was conducted on air-dried, ethylene glycol-solvated, and heated (550 °C) samples to distinguish between clay mineral species. Semi-quantitative estimates of clay mineral abundances were calculated using peak area measurements corrected with mineral-specific weighting factors.

The samples were vacuum-impregnated with blue-dyed epoxy resin to aid in porosity determination. Polished thin sections were analysed using optical microscopy (Olympus BX60) equipped

Table 1: Summary of XRD and conventional core (petrophysical) analyses of the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone cored section of Well-X.

Sample Details		XRD Analysis										Petrophysics	
Serial no.	Depth (m)	Whole Rock Composition (% wt.)					Clay Fraction (% wt.)					Helium Porosity (%)	Gas Permeability (mD)
		Quartz	Clay Minerals	K-Feldspar	Albite	Dolomite	Hematite	Anhydrite	Illite	Kaolinite	Chlorite		
1	2207.70	58.0	6.0	6.0	7.0	23.0	0.0	0.0	72.0	28.0	0.0	6.7	0.02
2	2211.77	69.0	10.0	4.0	6.0	11.0	0.0	0.0	80.0	20.0	0.0	12.3	6.57
3	2221.51	51.0	7.0	5.0	7.0	30.0	0.0	0.0	79.0	21.0	0.0	8.7	0.19
4	2235.12	60.0	5.0	2.0	8.0	25.0	0.0	0.0	76.0	24.0	0.0	9.4	0.12
5	2239.70	64.0	9.0	4.0	9.0	14.0	0.0	0.0	59.0	18.0	23.0	12.7	1.91
6	2245.71	69.0	5.0	2.0	6.0	17.0	0.0	1.0	87.0	13.0	0.0	13.0	14.4

Figure 4: A) Core permeability versus average grain size of six LVS cored samples, showing the grain size range and their relationship with permeability. B) Ternary diagram after [26] showing the rock classification of the LVS studied samples in Well-X.

with a Zeiss Axiocam 305 colour digital microscope camera to determine the detrital and authigenic components and characterise the pore types. High-resolution backscattered electron (BSE) imaging scanning electron microscopy (SEM; TESCAN MIRA Field Emission Microscope) was used to examine textural features. For electron microscopy, polished thin sections were coated with carbon using a Quorum Q150T ES Plus. Additionally, thin sections were stained with Alizarin Red S and potassium ferricyanide to distinguish carbonates [23]. Cathodoluminescence (CL) was used to identify distinct phases of carbonate cement and to assess detrital quartz and feldspars.

Mineral constituents and optical porosity were quantified (Table 2) based on 500 points per thin section [24] using JMicroVision software [25]. Detrital compositions were plotted using the QFR classification diagram [26]. Aver-

age grain sizes were measured following [27]. Intergranular volume (IGV) defined as the sum of intergranular pore space, intergranular cement volumes and depositional matrix, was calculated according to [28]. Further parameters, such as porosity loss due to compaction (COPL) and porosity loss due to cementation (CEPL) were derived based on the IGV [29]. An initial porosity of 45% for unconsolidated sand was assumed [30].

Helium porosity and nitrogen gas permeability were measured by conventional core analysis at Panterra Geoconsultants B.V., Leiderdorp, the Netherlands. Mercury injection capillary pressure (MICP) analyses were performed on four selected subsamples to quantify pore throat size distribution at Panterra Geoconsultants B.V., Leiderdorp, the Netherlands. Carbon and oxygen isotope analysis of seven bulk samples, primarily containing (non-)ferroan dolomite cements, was carried out at the GeoZentrum Nordbay-

ern laboratory, Friedrich-Alexander University, Germany. Sample powders were reacted with 100% phosphoric acid at a temperature of 70 °C using a Gasbench II connected to a Thermo Fisher Delta V Plus mass spectrometer. All values were reported in the delta notation (δ) per mil (‰) relative to the deviation from the Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) international standard and corrected for acid fractionation.

4. Results

4.1. Macroscopic Observations

The LVS predominantly exhibits moderate red-orange-pink colours. The cored section comprises sandstones with 2-7 m thick beds and range from (very) fine- to medium-grained, with characteristic high- to low-angle cross-bedding, horizontal lamination and/or being structureless. These sandstones often exhibit

Table 2: Summary of point count analysis of the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone cored section of Well-X. M = moderate; MG = moderately good; A = angular; SA = subangular; SR = subrounded; R = rounded; intergranular volume = IGv; compactional porosity loss = COPL; cementation porosity loss = CEPL.

Sample Details		Point Count Analysis														Texture					
Sample ID	Depth (m)	Quartz	Feldspar	Rock Fragments	Mica	Dolomite Grains	Ooids grains	Quartz Overgrowth	Dolomite Cement	Anhydrite	Illite	Kaolinite	Fe-oxide/hydroxide	Point counted Porosity	IGV	COPL	CEPL	Avg. grain size (µm)	Class	Sorting	Grain Shape
1	2205.75	56.1	5.8	7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	4.3	12.3	0.0	2.3	0.0	3.1	8.6		20.7	17.4	132	Very fine	M-G	A-SR
2	2206.38	55.7	5.2	5.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	6.7	9.8	0.0	4.8	0.0	9.0	3.0	33.3	17.5	25.0	122	Very fine	M	A-SR
3	2207.40	49.6	3.6	6.3	0.0	1.5	0.0	3.2	16.0	0.0	3.8	0.0	11.0	5.0	39.0	9.8	30.7	84	Very fine	M-G	A-SR
4	2207.70	44.0	3.2	4.6	0.0	1.0	0.0	2.7	37.9	0.3	0.0	0.3	0.3	5.7	47.2	1.0	38.7	114	Very fine	M-G	SA-R
5	2208.65	50.6	4.9	8.1	0.6	0.0	0.0	5.1	12.6	0.0	2.0	0.0	7.8	8.3	35.8	14.3	23.6	125	Very fine	M-G	SA-R
6	2211.62	49.5	4.3	19.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.3	6.9	0.0	1.0	0.0	8.0	7.9	27.1	24.6	14.5	115	Very fine	M-G	A-SR
7	2211.77	42.0	3.8	19.3	0.3	1.7	0.0	7.7	11.0	0.7	1.0	0.3	2.0	10.2	32.9	18.0	18.6	217	medium	M	A-SR
8	2214.47	49.2	3.5	17.4	0.6	0.0	0.0	1.7	8.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	8.6	10.0	29.3	22.2	15.0	187	Fine	M	A-SR
9	2221.51	42.0	2.6	11.6	0.3	15.0	0.0	2.3	20.6	0.0	0.5	0.0	0.8	4.3	28.5	23.1	18.6	144	Very fine	M-G	A-SR
10	2222.80	51.3	2.8	9.0	0.5	0.0	0.0	4.9	14.0	0.0	1.0	0.0	10.2	6.3	36.4	13.5	26.0	72	Very fine	M-G	A-SR
11	2228.30	47.0	3.3	7.8	0.0	0.0	3.5	3.9	13.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	14.9	6.2	38.4	10.7	28.8	78	Very fine	M	A-SR
12	2228.30	51.1	3.3	8.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	2.4	11.4	0.0	0.8	0.0	11.5	11.0	37.1	12.6	22.8	78	Very fine	M	A-SR
13	2233.40	43.7	2.7	9.7	0.5	1.0	17.5	1.3	18.1	0.3	1.4	0.0	0.8	3.0	24.9	26.8	16.0	155	Fine	M	A-SR
14	2235.12	35.4	3.3	9.5	0.7	1.0	16.3	4.7	21.0	1.0	0.0	0.0	0.7	6.4	33.8	16.9	22.8	137	Very fine	M	A-SR
15	2237.47	52.0	3.9	13.4	1.2	2.3	0.6	4.1	8.7	1.2	4.6	0.0	1.3	6.7	26.6	25.1	14.9	139	Fine	M-G	A-SR
16	2239.70	42.0	3.2	14.5	0.0	4.0	3.3	5.3	12.6	0.0	3.5	0.3	1.5	9.8	33.0	17.9	19.0	125	Fine	M-G	SA-R
17	2243.70	54.8	3.7	15.1	0.3	0.0	0.0	2.7	9.7	2.0	4.0	0.0	1.0	6.7	26.1	25.6	14.4	137	Very fine	M	A-SR
18	2245.71	38.0	3.6	10.0	0.0	8.0	5.3	4.3	12.6	2.3	3.7	0.7	0.3	11.2	35.1	15.3	20.3	192	Fine	M-G	A-SR
19	2246.12	53.6	4.1	11.6	0.1	0.0	0.0	4.7	11.0	0.1	3.1	0.0	0.3	11.5	30.7	20.7	15.2	219	Fine	M-G	A-SR
20	2248.70	51.6	3.4	14.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.3	15.9	1.5	2.3	0.0	1.5	9.4	30.9	20.4	17.1	204	Fine	M-G	A-SR

fining-upward sequences ranging from a few centimetres to meters in scale. Wavy bedding with root traces is locally observed. Pebbles and mud clasts are commonly present above erosive surfaces. Mud clasts are also abundant along other bedding planes throughout the cored section, and dolomite and anhydrite cements are locally recognised (Fig. 3).

4.2. Petrographical Analysis

LVS samples vary from very fine (62-125 µm) to fine (125-250 µm) and occasionally medium (250-500 µm) grained sandstone (Fig. 4A) with a subangular to rounded grain framework. They are moderately to well-sorted. Overall, the sandstones are classified as sublitharenite to litharenite (Fig. 4B). The LVS is predominantly composed of quartz grains (including mono- and polycrystalline quartz) making up on average 47.9% (min. 35.4%, max. 56.1%) (Fig. 5B). Quartz grains exhibit mostly light blue or dark-violet luminescence (Fig.

5B). Rock fragments are well represented with an average of 11.1% (min. 4.6%, max. 19.3%). These components predominantly consist of polycrystalline rock fragments of metamorphic origin (quartzite and schist) and sedimentary rock fragments. Feldspars (average 3.7%, min. 2.6%, max. 5.8%) predominantly consist of K-feldspar with blue to blotchy blue luminescence under CL (Fig. 5B). Plagioclase grains are less common (predominantly albite; Fig. 6E) and exhibit green luminescence under CL. Detrital dolomite grains locally are coated by iron-oxide/hydroxide-clay rims (Figs. 5A, B). These monocrystalline dolomite grains exhibit long to concave-convex contacts with quartz grains. Muscovite mica platelets are present in very low amounts (<1.0%). The modal mineralogical composition and average grain sizes of the studied samples are given in Table 2.

Non-ferroan dolomite (confirmed by Alizarin-K-ferricyanide staining) is the most abundant authigenic mineral and averaging 14.1% (min. 6.9%, max.

37.9%). The observed dolomite in the samples exhibits variable morphologies. Polycrystalline nodules (ooids) (~200 µm in diameter), often collapsed, with altered cores of (micro)porous dark micritic fabrics and iron-oxide/hydroxide-clay rims show concentric micritic to ghost laminations (Figs. 5C, D and 6A, B), surrounded by intergranular pore-filling dolomite overgrowths, which also occurs on other detrital grains (Figs. 5E, G). In addition, clusters of subhedral-euhedral crystal aggregates (Figs. 5A, B, E, F) and discrete rhombohedral crystals (Figs. 5F, H and 6C, D) are observed. Under CL both mono- to polycrystalline nodules and pore-filling dolomite exhibit a bright yellow-orange luminescence. Outer margins and, in some cases, internal crystal structures exhibit red luminescence (Figs. 5B, D, F). This dolomite crystal zonation is also confirmed by SEM observations (e.g. Fig. 5E). These nodules are particularly prevalent in the lower and middle parts of the studied cored interval.

Quartz overgrowths, averaging 3.7%

Figure 5: Photomicrographs of Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone (LVS) samples (blue = pore space/resin). PPL – plane-polarised light, CPL – cross-polarised light, CL – cathodoluminescence, SEM - scanning electron microscope.

A and B). A large portion of dolomite present as nodules (red arrows) and rhombohedral crystals (green arrows) and predominantly exhibiting bright yellow-orange luminescence. Quartz overgrowths (black arrows) can be identified with a well-developed brown rim between the quartz grains (Qz) and overgrowths. The CL image displays light-dark violet luminescence of quartz grains (Qz) while K-feldspar grains (Fsp) shows blue shades that have been slightly etched/altered. Oversized and grain-shaped pores are secondary in origin (SP). Grain-grain contacts range from long to concave-convex.

C and D). The partially preserved concentric structure of the ooid (black arrows) often exhibits dissolved or altered cores. Recrystallisation/replacement by dolomite is evidenced by their ghost (brown colour) fabrics. Expanded overgrowth fabrics can also be observed. The dolomite phases experienced a higher degree of compaction than the quartz grains and exhibit concave-convex to long contact with quartz grains. Concentric layers can be separated by dull CL and a dissolved nucleus forming mouldic pores.

E). Dolomite cements (Do) and illite (ill) occlude the porosity and block the pore throats. The bright appearance around the rhombic crystal shows the recrystallisation and overgrowths. These bright lines and spots are relatively rich in iron content. Dolomite precipitation also occurred on the detrital grains. Oversized and grain-shaped pores are secondary in origin (SP).

F). A cluster of subhedral - euhedral dolomite crystals (orange arrows) in the pore space exhibits bright yellow-orange to red CL, suggesting recrystallisation and overgrowth. Presence of secondary porosity (SP) due to partial and/or complete dissolution of detrital grains.

G) Brownish Fe-oxide/hydroxide coatings are present around detrital quartz grains (Qz). Quartz overgrowths (black arrows) can be observed. Dolomite cement (Do) appears to obstruct the quartz overgrowths. Uncompacted framework (floating-point) grain-grain contacts indicate that early cementation hampered mechanical compaction and preserved the primary grain framework. H) Pore space filled by dolomite (Do) and anhydrite (An) cements.

Figure 6: A and B). The spherical grains (ooids) with altered cores of (micro) porous dark micrite and surrounding micritic to ghost lamination (red arrow) are recrystallised and overgrown (green arrow). Overgrowth of dolomite (yellow arrows) is apparent around the rhombic crystals.

C and D). Some of the euhedral dolomite crystal (Do) show evidence of partial dissolution that preferentially develops in overgrowth zones (yellow arrows). Dolomite crystals (Do) also hinder the development of quartz overgrowth. Notice the dark coloured Fe-oxide/hydroxide coatings preserved between the grain contacts (black arrows) as well as a faded Fe-oxide/hydroxide clay coating present between quartz (Qz) and quartz overgrowth.

E). Plagioclase (plg) fragment showing albite twinning. These are less common in the studied sandstones. Secondary porosity has developed due to grain dissolution (SP). F). Intergranular or mouldic pores containing pore-filling and grain replacive illite crystals (ill). Black arrows show the presence of dark coloured Fe-oxide/hydroxide clay coating between the grain contacts and faded or dissolved relicts around pore spaces. PPL - plane polarised light, CPL- cross polarised light.

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(min. 0.3%, max. 7.7%), can be distinguished by the presence of Fe-oxide/hydroxide coatings between the detrital quartz and quartz overgrowth (e.g. Figs. 5A, G). Fe-oxides/hydroxides averaging 4.8% (min. 0.0%, max. 15.6%) are present primarily as brownish grain coatings (Figs. 5G, 6D). Authigenic clays occur only in minor proportion. Illite forms pore-lining tangential and pore-filling fibrous morphologies and ranges from 0.0% to 4.8% (Figs. 5E, 6F). Kaolinite (<1%) is less common and is rarely observed in SEM images. Due to its fine grain size and low birefringence, it is generally not identifiable by polarised light microscopy. Anhydrite (max. 2.3%) is observed as pore-filling cement in a few sandstone horizons (Fig. 5H; Table 2).

Overall, sandstones with rigid grains exhibit mostly floating to point-grain-to-grain contacts, while those with ductile grains show predominantly long to concavo-convex grain-to-grain contacts. The intergranular volume (IGV) of all examined sandstones averages 32.8% (min. 24.9%, max. 47.2%). The compactional porosity loss and cementation porosity loss (COPL-CEPL) plot indicates porosity loss predominantly due to cementation (Fig. 7).

4.3. Stable Isotopes

The stable isotope data of bulk samples containing dolomite cement from Well-X are plotted alongside published data from wells in the surrounding areas (Fig. 8). The dolomites from the LVS in this study show a narrow range in both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (-4.54 to -2.97 ‰ VPDB) and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ (+1.95 to +0.59 ‰ VPDB) values (Fig. 8).

4.4. Petrophysical Analysis

Optical porosity of the twenty thin sections ranges from 3.0 to 11.5%, comprising both primary (intergranular) and secondary (intragranular) pore types. The total helium porosity, measured from six selected core plugs, ranges from 6.7 to 12.9%. Results from optical and helium porosity are positively correlated ($R^2 > 0.8$). Nitrogen gas permeability from the same plugs ranges from 0.02 to 14.36 mD. Porosity and permeability data are plotted on a graph from [31] (Fig. 9). MICP pore size distribution ranges from 1 to 15 μm (Fig. 10). The pore throat size decreases with an increasing grain fineness as well as greater amounts of authigenic cements.

Figure 7: Compactional loss (COPL) plotted against cementation loss (CEPL) after [29] for the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone cored section in Well-X. The diagonal line is the line of equal porosity loss by compaction and cementation. The diagram assumes an initial porosity of 45% [30].

5. Discussion

5.1. Depositional Environment

In continental deposits, particularly in cored sections, distinguishing individual depositional settings is quite challenging. Our observations of sublitharenite to litharenite sandstones with the combination of sedimentary features such as cross-bedding, subangular to rounded grains and fining upward sequences are strong evidence for a palaeo-fluvial environment. The dominance of very fine (62-125 μm) to fine (125-250 μm) and occasionally medium (250-500 μm) grained sandstones with low-angle cross-bedding, horizontal and wavy laminations, with occasional rootlets (Fig. 3), reflect a dominance of low energy deposits. Their alternation with structureless to high-angle cross bedded sandstones and the occurrence of erosive surfaces with pebbles and mud clasts (Fig. 3), reflect changes in energy within the system. These changes in energy are typical for braided river systems both in space and time. On the one hand, this variation relates to their relative position with regard to the main fluvial channel (space); on the other hand, it can be related to variations in channel discharge, caused by alternating wet and dry conditions. The studied sandstones of Well-X were predominantly deposited as ephemeral

fluvial channels or sheet floods, laterally from the higher energy main braided fluvial channel(s), as illustrated in Figure 11, in line with [1,5,7,11,20,21].

5.2. Diagenesis

Sandstone reddening

The precipitation of iron oxides/hydroxides present as grain coatings (Figs. 5A, G and 6D), which are responsible for the macro-scale red-orange-pink colour, is typically syn-depositional to eodiagenetic as observed even in present-day sediments in hot deserts or semi-arid environments [32]. Similar red-bed eodiagenetic features from the Permo-Triassic basins in the North Sea region have been described and interpreted accordingly [12,16,33-39]. The fact that the iron oxide/hydroxide coatings are present in nearly all of the examined samples indicates that no significant bleaching by reducing (mesodiagenetic) fluids occurred. This contrasts with LVS cored sections Q11-01, VAL-01, NWK-02, KDK-01, where only remnants of these coatings are present, and where the sandstones instead exhibit green, grey, and white colours. Interpreted diagenetic processes in the LVS samples of well-X are summarised in Figure 12.

Figure 8: Cross-plot of $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data from bulk samples containing dolomite cement from the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstones in Well-X plotted together with published data [12,10,14,16]. The dotted purple box shows the Middle/Late Triassic marine calcite signature [49], typical marine pore fluid (dotted black box) and typical meteoric pore water signatures, dotted brown box from [14]. L-blocks wells L02-02, L02-05, L02-06, L09-06 are located north of Well-X [10]; wells Gaag-02 (GAG-02), Werkendam-03 (WED-03), and Haastrecht-02 (HST-02) from [14] are located on the southern margin of the West Netherlands Basin; and wells KB-201 from [12] and KB-64, KB-98, KB-169, KB-172, KB-201 wells from [16] are in the northeast of the Campine Basin.

Coated grain versus nodular carbonates

In the literature, there has been considerable discussion on the origin of spherical carbonates found in the Buntsandstein sandstones. On the one hand, the spherical carbonates are described as glaebules and nodules, i.e., early diagenetic chemically grown carbonate spherules, that often coalesce and merge forming calcretes or dolocretes, depending on the carbonate's mineralogy [12,40,41,42,43]. On the other hand, the internal concentric lamination around a nucleus suggests a transport and/or reworking component in their formation and support their classification as coated grains. Depending on their morphology, they can be classified as ooids [10,44], with a distinct spheroidal morphology and undulose extinction over the radial crystal, as spheroids or oncooids, which display irregular thickness of the laminae attributed to preferential growth directions by a biological component in their formation [16]. Their classification is therefore directly related to their formation process and timing.

Based on our observations for Well-X

and similar carbonate features in the LVS cored sections of the VAL-01 and NWK-02 wells, a large part of the confusion and discussion in the literature can be related to their mixed origin. The ~200 μm spherical grains with altered cores of (micro)porous dark micrite and surrounding micritic to ghost lamination (Figs. 5C, D and 6A, B) are textbook examples of (often collapsed) ooids. They frequently display concavo-convex contacts with other grains (Fig. 5C) due to their susceptibility to compaction. They are overgrown, however, by radial sparite cements which can also be found on other detrital grains. The latter are associated with undercompacted fabrics characterised by floating to point grain contacts (Fig. 5G) related to displacive (i.e. nodular growth) (Fig. 6A, B). The latter is typical for formation under minimal overburden [45] and in soils, with nodules forming as an earlier stage of calcretes or dolocretes [12,40,41,42,43]. Carbonate precipitation occurs at the water table or within the soil's illuviated horizon, which tends to concentrate around a nucleus. Most likely the ooids acted as preferential precipitation sites.

Other typical pedogenic fabrics, such as possible rhizocretions, meniscus, and pendant cements, biologically induced structures (burrows, root traces), etc. could not unequivocally be recognised. In addition, it is difficult to identify typical pedogenic and phreatic features due to post-depositional alteration.

Considering the formation of ooids, which are often interpreted in the literature as typical marine deposits, [16] interpreted their formation in fluvial channels and bottom lags of ponds [46]. While these settings likely occurred in the braided fluvial setting, other origins are possible including soil, travertine, cave, and lake systems [47]. In addition, according to [48], such coatings may form on slopes, particularly on low-angle pediments, where grains are transported downslope by gravity and become evenly coated during transit, especially in warm, semi-arid climates. Depending on the formation processes and the conditions during formation, spheroid or ooid fabrics and/or their organisation will differ [47]. However, the faint preservation of micritic lamination in the larger dolomite spars of the coated grains as ghost structures testifies to some recrystallisation. Similar ghost outlines and recrystallisation features have also been described by [45]. The original fabrics are thus only minimally preserved, and therefore their chemical signature will most likely no longer be representative of their original depositional environment.

Dolomitisation

Whole-rock stable isotope data for the LVS sandstone samples, which primarily contain (non-)ferroan dolomite cements, but also the recrystallised ooids, form a tight cluster ($\delta^{18}\text{O} = -4.54$ to -2.97 ‰ VPDB, $\delta^{13}\text{C} = +1.95$ to $+0.59$ ‰ VPDB; Fig. 8). This indicates that the same or very similar fluids were responsible for both the recrystallisation as well as the overgrowth and pore-reducing cementation. This contrasts to the stable $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ - $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ isotope signature of Buntsandstein lithologies of other studies in the southern Netherlands [12,14,16] with exception of well L02-06 [10] (Fig. 8). The signature for Well-X is close to the Middle/Late Triassic marine signature (dotted purple box in Fig. 6) [49]. Typical meteoric signatures, as expected for continental settings, are more depleted both in $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ values, typically sourced from meteoric waters containing atmospheric or soil-derived CO_2 (dotted

Figure 9: Core permeability versus core porosity plotted on a graph from [31].

Figure 10: MICP pore size distribution of four Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone samples, with pore throat sizes from 0.01 to 15 µm. The red curve corresponds to a sample with a 192 µm average grain size and lowest percentage of authigenic cements (18%), with a higher pore throat size dominance. The black curve represents a sample with an average grain size of 125 µm and 19% authigenic cement content. The blue curve corresponds to a sample with a 144 µm average grain size and 23% authigenic cements. The brown curve represents a sample with a finer average grain size of 137 µm and the highest cement content of 27%, with significantly smaller dominant pore throat sizes.

brown box in Fig. 6). Other studies explain their signature's deviation from a typical meteoric signature by strongly evaporative conditions [16]. At 25°C, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of -8.5 to -6 ‰ VPDB are expected for carbonates in equilibrium with typical Triassic meteoric water (-6 ‰ VSMOW) and strongly evaporated waters (+3 ‰ VSMOW), respectively [50]. The well-X signatures are significantly higher than

this range (Fig. 8). In addition, while a marine signature in a continental deposit might initially seem controversial, based on the stratigraphy of the study area, the partially enclosed marine to evaporitic deposits of the Rot Formation, related to Middle/Late Triassic marine incursions [11], directly overlie the Solling Formation which lies on top of the Volpriehausen Formation in Well-X (Fig. 2).

The dolomite, in combination with its marine isotopic signature can be explained by different seawater dolomitisation models. Seawater dolomitisation by slope convection would require an atoll or elevated structure [51]. Mixing zone (Dorag) dolomitisation occurs when fresh groundwater mixes with brine in deep burial settings leading to supersaturation and carbonate precipitation [52]. This process would result in varying isotopic signatures in combination with textures with varying cathodoluminescence. In contrast, the overgrowths and/or recrystallisation of the observed dolomite are relatively uniform and range from bright yellow-orange to red luminescence (Figs. 5B, D, F). The bright yellow-orange luminescence suggests Mn^{2+} as the luminescent activator, as proposed by [53]. Detailed SEM-EDS analysis reveals that red luminescent zones are related to a relatively higher Fe^{2+} concentrations, suggesting that iron was incorporated into the carbonate matrix. These zones are commonly formed as syntaxial overgrowths on eodiagenetic cements and have low iron content in the outer rims of the rhombic crystals (Figs. 5E and 6C, D). The spatial association of these red luminescent dolomite zones with remnants of Fe-oxide/hydroxide coatings implies that these coatings likely served as a significant Fe^{2+} source. These petrographic observations in combination with the presence of the overlying marine to sabkha Rot deposits, points to a reflux dolomitisation model driven by evaporative pumping. This model suggests that density-driven brine migration and the influx of Mg-rich saline water during evaporation was the most plausible dolomite formation mechanism in such settings [51,54,55]. The presence of calcite cements in the neighbouring wells (e.g. NWK-02) and those reported by [45] support the reflux dolomitisation model, in which often stratiform or tongue-like bodies of dolomitising fluids follow preferential vertical and lateral flow paths (Fig. 14).

In terms of timing, the direct superposition of the dolomite crystals on the iron oxide/hydroxide rims, preventing quartz overgrowth (Fig. 5E, G), supports dolomite formation prior to quartz overgrowths. Furthermore, scattered isolated rhombic crystals locally filling framework grain dissolution sites, commonly related to the alteration of detrital feldspar grains, show that these dolomites formed during relatively early mesodiagenesis. The reported Broad Fourteens

Figure 11: Conceptual depositional model showing the idealised palaeogeographic location of the studied wells (produced by AI engine and modified in CoreIDRAW).

Figure 12: Summary of interpreted major diagenetic processes of the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone of Well-X.

Basin burial history (with e.g., thermal subsidence and uplift) [5,7,11] suggests that dolomitisation occurred during the Middle/Late Triassic marine incursion, following significant erosion of overlying strata related to the Hardeggen unconformity, at shallow burial depths (<100 metres based on the overlying strata; Fig. 2). The expanded fabrics of the dolomites are also indicative of minimal overburden. Displacive growth of carbonates can occur at depths of up to several tens or possibly hundreds of meters [56,57,58].

Anhydrite and quartz overgrowth

Anhydrite predominantly occurs as a poikilotopic intergranular pore-filling cement in specific horizons. The anhydrites postdate dolomitisation since they locally enclose dolomite cements (Figs. 5H, 6D) and when present, inhibit the otherwise omnipresent quartz overgrowth. In addition, the absence of hydrocarbon inclusions within these

anhydrite crystals supports their formation prior to hydrocarbon migration. [10] reported that anhydrite was recycled from the underlying Zechstein in the L-blocks, but a Zechstein succession is absent in our study area. Although gypcrettes are common features in arid and semi-arid environments [59], they were not observed in the analysed core samples. Given that significant portions of early diagenetic gypsum cements may dissolve during burial, early-formed gypsum remains a plausible source for later anhydrite cementation during deeper diagenesis.

Syntaxial quartz overgrowths can be distinguished by preserved Fe-oxide/hydroxide-clay coatings between the detrital grains and the overgrowths (Figs. 5A, G). Locally, overgrowths interlock to form a rigid grain framework. The development of quartz overgrowths depends on the pore space present around the detrital grains. These overgrowths are discontinuous and anhedral, having

formed in competitive environments where dolomite and, locally, anhydrite had already precipitated.

Processes for illite formation and hydrocarbon charging

Smectite-to-illite transformation is a well-known reaction process in the Buntsandstein. It occurs generally at shallow depths due to intense dissolution by meteoric water or increased acidity [16,60] and leads to a steady increase in illite. In addition, the paucity of kaolinite in contrast with the hairy, whiskery, and platy illites in the pores (Figs. 5E, 6F), indicates that feldspar alteration directly resulted in increased illite formation (related to the K^+/H^+ activity ratio) [61]. Illitisation of kaolinite would have required high temperatures, corresponding to burial depths >4000 meters [60], which significantly exceeds the maximum depth (~3000m) attained during burial of the studied sandstones [3,5]. The exact timing of illitisation is difficult to establish, however, its presence in secondary pores suggests it developed after hydrocarbon migration. Fibrous and meshwork type illite precipitation in the pore space likely obstructed pore throats (Fig. 5E) and prevented efficient fluid migration. According to [3,5,11,62], hydrocarbon charging in the Buntsandstein reservoirs probably occurred during Early Cretaceous.

While hydrocarbons are known as reducing agents that cause dissolution and bleaching of iron-rich sandstones [35,63,64,65,66], the overall preservation of Fe-oxide/hydroxide coatings (Figs. 5A, C, G and 6D) and only partial dissolution of some of the euhedral dolomite crystals (Figs. 6C, D) testifies to overall low reactivity. Furthermore, lack of pyrite and absence of significantly depleted $\delta^{13}C$ values (e.g., < -25 ‰ VPDB) [67], show that hydrocarbons did not induce strongly altering chemical processes in these sandstones. Most likely, since Well-X is a dry gas well with very low water production, the gas in the sandstones prevented penetration of reactive fluids.

5.3. Reservoir Quality

The Buntsandstein is known in many locations as a good to very good reservoir. To a large extent this is governed by early diagenetic framework-stabilising cements. While these initially reduce porosity significantly, they hinder

Figure 13: Porosity-depth diagram illustrating the porosity evolution during burial of the LVS of Well-X. Porosity at the time of deposition is a function of sorting and matrix, with clean, randomly packed sands having up to about 42% - 48% porosity [31]. Eodiagenetic cementation decreased initial porosity and stabilised the framework. The Hardegsen unconformity, with erosion related to an uplift and subsequent reflux dolomitisation at relatively shallow depth, further decreased the porosity. Further depth related diagenetic processes, such as anhydrite cementation and quartz overgrowth reduce porosity. Hydrocarbon migration may have led to some dissolution and relatively slight local increase in porosity in the sandstones.

mechanical compaction during burial, ultimately resulting in relatively higher porosities (Fig. 13). In addition, subsequent dissolution, often associated with bleaching, can further increase porosity and permeability. However, the LVS sandstones of Well-X show a different behaviour (Fig. 9).

The positive correlation between porosity, permeability, and grain size is confirmed for the present dataset,

implying that the dominance of (very) fine-grained lithologies can be directly associated with reduced reservoir properties. Samples with relatively higher grain sizes with lower content of fine sediments and diagenetic cements (18%), exhibit larger pore throat sizes (5-15 μm). In contrast, samples with higher content of finer sediments and diagenetic cements (27%), show significantly smaller dominant pore throat sizes (<2 μm). In addition,

the lowest porosity (<10%) and permeability (0.02mD) values are related to carbonate fabrics (max. 38% by point counting; Table 2). Quartz overgrowths (max. 8% by point counting; Table 2) and fibrous to meshwork-type illite precipitation in the pore space, further obstruct pore throats (Figs. 5E, 6F), decreasing permeability and preventing efficient fluid flow. These observations align with petrophysical results of LVS cored sections from the VAL-01, NWK-02, KDK-01 wells, where significant concentration of various diagenetic cements correlated with reduced reservoir quality due to pore-occluding and pore-throat-blocking cements [13].

In comparison to other sandstones, diagenetic processes thus affected porosity differently in Well-X (Fig. 13). Although stabilising cements were also observed in Well-X, the significant decrease in porosity was even more apparent due to further cementation and dolomitisation. Secondary porosity generated by partial and complete dissolution of detrital grains such as feldspars or rock fragments, as evidenced by remaining grain coatings and the presence of oversized pores (Figs. 5A, E, G), is only locally observed and therefore generally limited.

5.4. Reservoir implications

The reduced reservoir quality observed in the studied LVS cored section is primarily controlled by both the depositional system and subsequent diagenetic processes. Understanding these factors

Figure 14: conceptual models illustrating the effect of depositional environments (A) and reflux dolomitisation (B) on porosity in the study area. Microscopic images, A-I shows moderate to well sorted grains with relatively larger grain sizes, characteristic of proximal channel deposits. A-II represents distal floodplain deposits dominated by finer-grained sediments. B-I and B-II highlight the predominance of dolomite cements due to reflux dolomitisation, influencing reservoir quality in the studied sections.

provides insight into the spatial variability of porosity and permeability, which is crucial for reservoir prediction.

The depositional setting exerts a significant control over the initial porosity and permeability distribution, thereby influencing reservoir potential across different sections of the fluvial system. In braided fluvial systems, proximal channel sands or confined channel sections typically exhibit the highest reservoir quality due to moderate to well sorting and relatively larger grain size distributions (Figure 14A-I). In contrast, distal parts of the fluvial river system, such as floodplain sections, are often dominated by finer-grained sediments, resulting in reduced reservoir quality in Well-X (Figure 14A-II). Local depositional controls, including changes in sediment supply, flow regime, and accommodation space, further modulate porosity and permeability patterns within these depositional environments.

Diagenetic alterations, particularly cementation and compaction, have a profound impact on the reduced reservoir quality of these sandstones. In the studied sections, dolomite cements formed through an evaporative or tidal pumping mechanism, driven by density-induced flow. The reflux dolomitisation model involves the downward migration of magnesium-rich brines through the sediment layers, resulting in dolomite precipitation in tongue-like or stratiform bodies within the reservoir [68] (Fig. 14A).

Generally, dolomitisation of calcite is associated with a reduction in crystal volume, and thus a slight increase in porosity and often improved permeability [51,68,69]. In Well-X, however, the reservoir quality contradicts the typical porosity benefits associated with dolomite formation due to the extensive recrystallisation and overgrowths that fill pore spaces (Fig. 14B-I and II). The dominance of porosity-reducing dolomite cementation in Well-X highlights the complexity of diagenetic controls and their potential to either enhance or reduce reservoir quality.

Predicting reservoir properties in Buntsandstein reservoirs thus requires an integrated reservoir model that accounts for both the depositional facies distribution and diagenetic geographic controls, with the latter proving to be perhaps most challenging. Based on the reconstructed location of the paleo-coastline and inferred sabkha environment (suggested by the Rot deposits), brine lobe or

tongue infiltration can be reconstructed. The density-driven downward migration, however, will follow preferential flow paths, not only controlled by depositional conditions but also by earlier diagenetic alterations and tectonics. Areas lacking large-scale faults with an intact shielding clay layer (upper Volpriehausen clay/siltstone) or sandstones positioned deeper than several hundred metres at the moment of brine migration will not have been affected. On the other hand, where brine migration occurs, reservoir reduction would be catalysed by preferential precipitation on carbonate features (e.g. ooids) which act as nucleation sites. This model aligns with the contrasting reservoir quality of neighbouring fields.

6. Conclusions

This study examined the impact of sedimentology and diagenesis that control reduced reservoir quality in a 49.09 m cored section of the Lower Volpriehausen Sandstone (LVS) from offshore Well-X (exact location kept confidential). To highlight both local and regional scale variations, the published data from surrounding wells were used. The key conclusions drawn from this study are as follows:

In Well-X, the LVS deposits mainly reflect deposition in a paleo-fluvial setting. The dominance of very fine (62-125 μm) to fine (125-250 μm) grains, along with typical sedimentary features, suggests deposition primarily in ephemeral fluvial channels or distal floodplain settings, associated with a braided river system. In contrast, LVS cored sections in the KDK-01 and VAL-01 wells, which show better reservoir properties, indicate deposition in confined channels and more proximal floodplain settings.

Ooids, which are common constituents of the LVS framework grains are recrystallised and overgrown by nodular radial sparite cements associated with under-compacted fabrics characterised by floating to point grain contacts. These features exhibit lower reservoir potential, making their identification crucial for predicting poor reservoir performance in subsurface activities.

Petrographic observations reveal a complex diagenetic evolution with multiphases of cementation that vary both in content and extent. Eodiagenetic carbonate fabrics in Well-X reduced initial porosity but played a crucial role in stabilising the grain framework by hindering mechanical compaction. Uncompacted

framework, such as floating to point grain-to-grain contacts, provide indirect evidence of their former presence. A similar early diagenetic evolution, likely involving the preservation of the primary grain framework through early (calcite/dolomite/sulphate) cementation is reported from surrounding wells.

Stable isotope data of the carbonates in the sandstone samples, which primarily consist of (non-)ferroan dolomite cements, show a marine signature. Together with evidence for the Middle to Late Triassic marine transgression, preserved in the lithostratigraphic column as overlying marine and sabkha Rot deposits, and evidence of significant erosion of interlayered strata (Hardeggen uniformity), support reflux dolomitisation.

This highlights the role of marine fluids in the study area in shaping the diagenetic evolution and ultimately reducing reservoir quality of the LVS or Main Buntsandstein Subgroup. Moreover, this study highlights the need to develop a comprehensive model to more precisely delineate the extent and intensity of the sabkha-marine influence in order to better understand its impact on the reservoir quality of Buntsandstein reservoirs.

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